

LINGUOCULTUROLOGY AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. *This article provides a detailed overview of linguoculturology, highlighting its importance in understanding the connection between language and culture, especially in the context of globalization. It traces the historical development of linguoculturology, emphasizing its interdisciplinary connections with ethnolinguistics and sociolinguistics.*

Keywords: *linguoculturology; culture; language; linguistics; society.*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur tezisdagi lingvokulturologiya haqida batafsil ma'lumot beriladi hamda uning til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni tushunishdagi ahamiyatini, ayniqsa globallashuv sharoitida, ta'kidlaydi. Unda lingvokulturologiyaning tarixiy rivojlanishi hamda uning etnolingvistika va sosiolingvistika kabi fanlar bilan o'zaro aloqalari yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *lingvokulturologiya; madaniyat; til; tilshunishlik; jamiyat.*

Аннотация. *Эта статья предоставляет подробный обзор лингвокультурологии, подчеркивая её важность для понимания взаимосвязи языка и культуры, особенно в период глобализации. В ней прослеживается историческое развитие лингвокультурологии и подчеркивается её междисциплинарные связи с этнолингвистикой и социоллингвистикой.*

Ключевые слова: *лингвокультурология; культура; язык; лингвистика; общество.*

In the era of active globalization, when countries continue to build and strengthen their relations, the need to study world cultures and their traditions is increasing day by day. Linguoculturology is a branch of linguistics that studies the relationship between language and culture. It studies diverse issues related to understanding the cultural picture of the world, linguistic consciousness and the image of the world. It closely related with ethnolinguistics and sociolinguistics, but what sets linguoculturology apart is its focus on both historical and modern cultural features of language.

The term "linguoculturology" emerged in Russian linguistics in the late XX century in connection with the works of the phraseological school headed by V. N. Teliya, the works of Yu.S.Stepanov, N. D.Arutyunova, V. V. Vorobyov, V. I. Shaklein, V. A. Maslova, A.D. Shmelev, V. G. Kostomarov, N. I. Tolstoy [2;9]. However, it is important to note that the problem of language and culture had been a topic of interest of scholars since the beginning of the XIX century. The German scientists, the brothers Grimm, tried to solve these problems, whose ideas found their development in Russia in the 60-70s of the XIX century [3,21].

Linguoculturology as a distinct scientific field has developed in Russian linguistics. A number of Russian linguists have devoted their books and scientific research to this topic. It is also worth noting that in different scientific sources this branch of science is designated by different terms such as linguoculturology and cultural linguistics.

Scholars still continue to debate its status. Some regard it as a cultural discipline, linking it to ethnography, while others see it as a linguistic field with roots in the theories of W von Humboldt and W. Wundt.

There are two main directions in the study of linguoculturology:

A) Linguistic personality

B) Language as a system of semiotic representation of cultural values [1;29].

The primary focus of linguoculturology is on the subjective aspects of culture, that is, those cultural features of the language that we cannot see or touch [5;43]. The study of the subjective elements of culture is necessary when building international relationships, negotiating treaties, or engaging in cross-cultural communication. People often perceive others from the perspective of their own culture, which can lead to misunderstandings and conflicts between different ethnic groups.

For example, Russian and Thai communication styles are different from each other. Students from Thailand stopped attending lectures on Russian literature because they felt uncomfortable with the Russian teaching style, which was louder and more direct than they were accustomed to. They described their teacher as "yelling", which was perceived negatively compared to the more reserved communication they were used to [4;21].

To avoid such cross-cultural misunderstandings, it is crucial to study the customs and communication styles of your potential interlocutors or business partners. This can be achieved by learning online resources and specialized dictionaries, such as:

- Cultural dictionaries
- Explanatory dictionaries with historical and cultural information
- Functional and cognitive dictionaries
- Foreign language dictionaries

From the above, it can be concluded that a lack of knowledge in linguoculturology makes it challenging to build strong relationships with people from other cultures. Therefore, continued study of linguoculturology and sociolinguistics is essential for effective cross-cultural communication.

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